

Ayurvedic Management of *Kaphaj Abhishyanda* with Special Reference to Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis - A Case Study

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ABSTRACT: Allergic Conjunctivitis is a common clinical condition faced by practitioners. Simple allergic conjunctivitis is a mild and recurrent condition. Nonspecific allergic conjunctivitis is characterized by itching, hyperaemia and mild papillary response. The major complaints of simple allergic conjunctivitis are intense itching, burning sensation, lacrimation, photophobia and watery, stringy discharge. Mast cell stabilizers, topical Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and steroids are the available treatment options that too with symptomatic relief and potential side effects, which limits the long-term use of these medicines. This condition can be correlated with *Kaphaj Abhishyanda* in *Ayurvedic* texts. Owing to the symptoms and signs, the case was diagnosed as *Kaphaj Abhishyanda*/Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis. Hence this patient was treated with *Kriyakalpa* (ocular therapeutic procedures) *Triphala*, *Shunthi*, *Nimba*, *Lodhra* and *Atarushaka Kwatha Aashchyotan* which gave significant results and found useful in the management of Simple allergic conjunctivitis.

KEYWORDS: *Kaphaj Abhishyanda*, *Kriyakalpa*, Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis.

INTRODUCTION

Simple allergic conjunctivitis is the most common form of ocular allergy. It is a hypersensitivity reaction to specific airborne antigens. Basically, it is an urticarial reaction. The distressing signs and symptoms may cause extreme discomfort to the patients; it can disturb the patient's routine life. Simple allergic conjunctivitis, is a type-I immediate hypersensitivity reaction mediated by IgE and subsequent mast cell activation, following exposure of ocular surface to airborne allergens. Family history of atopy might be present.^[1] Although the disease does not affect the vision, it is an extremely discomforting disease. Drugs used in treatment of Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis have multiple pharmacological actions, such as histamine H1 receptor antagonists, mast cell stabilizers, inhibit infiltration activation and degranulation of eosinophils, and other late phase reactions, such as the effect of platelet activating factors, which are useful in the treatment of simple allergic conjunctivitis. These are expensive and possibilities of relapses are also present. Moreover, these drugs are to be used for a long period of time to keep the condition under control, hence, there is scope to search for a better remedy from the rich heritage of ophthalmic preparations available in Ayurveda.

Kaphaj Abhishyanda is one of the types of *Netra Abhishyanda* mentioned in *Ayurved Samhitas*. The word *Abhishyanda* is derived from two words viz "Abhi" means profuse or more and "Syandana" means

discharge or secretions, combined meaning is profuse discharge from all parts of the eye. *Kaphaj Abhishyanda* characterized by *Ushnabhinanda*: Longing for warmth (Comforts), *Guruta*: Heaviness, *Kandu*: Itching, *Upadeha*: Stickiness due to increased exudates (Thickening), *Sitata*: Whiteness, *Atisaityam*: Excessive coldness, *Stravomuhuh*: Frequent discharge, *Pischil*: Slimy,^[2] which are very similar to most of the signs and symptoms of Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis.

Based on the similarities of signs and symptoms, *Kaphaj Abhishyanda* can be co-related with Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis. Thus, there is an increasing need to understand the disease in view of Ayurveda and to establish the management through Ayurvedic system of medicine.

CASE REPORT

A male patient, age 45 years, visited to OPD of *Shalakyatantra* department, G.A.C And Hospital, Nanded on 30/04/2025 with chief complaint of *Kandu*(itching), *Akshirag*(redness), lid oedema and *strav* (watery and sticky secretion) in both eyes for 4-5days and history of recurrences.

He was diagnosed as case of simple allergic conjunctivitis and took medicine at another hospital but not satisfied, and then he came to G.A.C And Hospital, Nanded.

Consent: Implied consent taken.

Personal History:

There was no specific family history of the patient. A general examination revealed normal physiological findings.

Samanya Parikshan:

Pulse: 70/min

Blood Pressure: 120/70 mm Hg

Afebrile

Vishesh Parikshan:

Slit lamp examination revealed the presence of hyperaemia and papillae in the palpebral conjunctiva and hyperaemia and chemosis which was giving a swollen juicy appearance to the bulbar conjunctiva. The rest of the eye assessment was normal.

Ocular examination findings before treatment dated 30/4/25

Structure	Examination	Right Eye	Left Eye
Eyelid	Oedema	Mild oedema	Mild oedema
Conjunctiva	Palpebral Conjunctiva Bulbar Conjunctiva	Hyperaemia, papillae Hyperaemia, chemosis	Hyperaemia, papillae Hyperaemia, chemosis
Cornea	Transparency	Clear	Clear
Anterior Chamber	Depth	Normal	Normal
Pupil	Shape and Size and Reaction	NSRL	NSRL
Lens	Transparency	WNL	WNL

Visual acuity

Eye	With Spect Vision	Distant Vision	Pin Hole Vision
Right Eye	6/9p	6/18p	6/9
Left Eye	6/9	6/18	6/9
Both Eye	6/6p		
Near Vision	N/6		

Line of treatment:

The patient was treated with *Netra Kriyakalpa* (eye procedure) like *Aashchyotan* (The process of instillation of liquid medicine drop by drop in the *kaninika sandhi* i.e. Inner Canthus from a height of two *Angulas*). The details of the medications administered are depicted as shown in Table.

Sr No	Date	Advice <i>Kriyakalpa</i> Procedure - <i>Aashchyotan</i>	Observation
1	30/4/2025 to 7/5/2025	<i>Triphala, Shunthi, Nimba, Lodhra and Atarushaka Kwatha Aashchyotan</i> [3] Duration – for 7 days	Itching, watering, lid oedema reduced in 7 days
2	30/4/2025 to 15/5/2025	<i>Triphala, Shunthi, Nimba, Lodhra and Atarushaka Kwatha Aashchyotan</i> Duration – 15 days	hyperaemia, Papillae reduced After 15 days

Before Treatment

After Treatment

Follow up finding:

	Before Treatment	After 7 days of Treatment	After 15 days of Treatment
Hyperaemia	+++	+	-
Itching	+++	+	-
Lid Oedema	++	-	-
Papillae	+++	++	+
Watery Discharge	++	-	-

DISCUSSION

Allergic conjunctivitis is one of the most common problems seen by ophthalmologists worldwide. *Abhishyanda* is included in *Sarvagata Netraroga* which affects eye similar to symptoms of conjunctivitis. *Acharya Sushruta* has mentioned in the 6th chapter of *Uttartantra* that, *Abhishyanda* (conjunctivitis) is the causative factor for all eye diseases and, if neglected, leads to other serious complications such as *Adhimantha* (glaucoma), *akshishopha* (inflammations/swelling of eye parts) etc^[4]. Hence *Abhishyanda* (conjunctivitis) should be treated by giving due importance to protect the eyes from further complications.

As discussed earlier, the patient of *Kaphaj Abhishyanda*/Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis was treated with *Aashchyotan*. *Acharya Vagbhat* stated that “*sarvesham akshi roganam Aashchyotanm hitam*”^[5] means *Aashchyotan* is one of the best treatments among all *kriyakalpas*. It is first *Kriyakalpa* to be performed in eye diseases, especially in *Abhishyanda*. It can be performed in *amavastha* also. According to Ayurveda, the *Aashchyotan* penetrates into *Akshikosha Srotas*, *Shira Srotas*, *Ghrana Srotas* and *Mukha Srotas* of the *Urdhvanga Bhaga* and remove the mala present there. After absorption of eye drop may undergo systemic distribution primarily by nasal mucosa absorption and possible by local ocular distribution by transcorneal/transconjunctival absorption and metabolism of eye drops by various enzymes. Hence after instillation of eye drops, these fluids undergo absorption, distribution and metabolism. So, effect of eye drops is local as well as systemic.

Here we used *Triphala*, *Shunthi*, *Nimba*, *Lodhra* and *Atarushaka Kwatha Aashchyotan*. This *Kalpa* is mentioned in *Astanga Samgraha Uttara Sthana*. Their combined pharmacological action of *Kapha-Pitta Hara*, *Kandughna*, *Dahaprashaman*, *Ropan*, *Shothahara* (anti-inflammatory action), and *Vedanahar*, *Chakshushya*, and *Sankochak* has a potency to relieve the clinical features.

CONCLUSION

Kaphaj Abhishyanda (Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis) is a benign, but distressing ailment which can be better managed / treated with a simple, safe, non-toxic, cheap, and effective Ayurvedic formulation. Symptoms associated with *Kaphaj Abhishyanda* can be effectively relieved by *Triphala*, *Shunthi*, *Nimba*, *Lodhra* and *Atarushaka Kwatha Aashchyotan*. Ayurvedic drugs used in this treatment are easily available. Timely use of this treatment modality in this case of Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis found effective. This overall regimen did not cause any unwanted effects. Further trials may be conducted to standardize these treatment protocols.

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